

INSTRUCTIONAL EXPERIENCES IN TEACHING VOLLEYBALL – THE CASE OF NON-MAPEH TEACHERS IN PUBLIC HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

Teaching volleyball presents distinct challenges for non-MAPEH (Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health) teachers, particularly when they are assigned to teach outside their specialization—a common occurrence in public secondary schools with limited staffing and resources. This study investigates the instructional experiences of non-MAPEH teachers in the Division of Valencia City, Philippines, focusing on the difficulties they face, their coping strategies, and recommendations for improving volleyball instruction. Using case study design, data were collected through in-depth interviews with selected participants. The findings revealed that non-MAPEH teachers experience emotional and instructional difficulties, such as anxiety, lack of confidence, and uncertainty due to their limited content knowledge and pedagogical training in physical education. Moreover, challenges related to inadequate sports facilities, lack of instructional materials, and minimal financial support hinder effective volleyball instruction. Despite these barriers, teachers displayed resilience by engaging in self-directed learning through digital platforms, sports-related media, self-assessment, and participation in professional development activities such as seminars and workshops. While these adaptive strategies helped fill knowledge gaps, the study concludes that these are not sufficient in isolation. The research recommends institutional interventions, including targeted training, structured mentorship, improved resource allocation, and curriculum development tailored to non-specialist teachers. Future research may examine the long-term impact of training, mentorship, and peer collaboration on the competence and confidence of non-MAPEH teachers in teaching volleyball. It may also

explore student learning outcomes and engagement, as well as extend to other team sports to better understand out-of-field teaching in physical education.

Keywords: *Non-MAPEH teachers, Volleyball instruction, Physical education, Out-of-field teaching, Teacher training*

INTRODUCTION

Physical education (PE) remains an essential component of holistic education, contributing significantly to students' physical, emotional, cognitive, and social development (Hobbs & Porsch, 2021; Solis, 2024). Recognized globally, PE fosters lifelong health habits, teamwork skills, and emotional well-being among students (Buedron, 2018; Mesias, 2022). However, a persistent and growing issue is the assignment of non-specialist, or out-of-field, teachers to deliver specialized PE subjects such as volleyball—a trend observed across both developed and developing nations (Hobbs & Porsch, 2021; Katigbak & Andal, 2023; Silvestre & Itaas, 2020). Out-of-field teaching affects instructional quality, teacher confidence, and student outcomes, posing critical challenges for educational systems worldwide (Dulay, 2022; Mesias & Pelicano, 2024). Understanding the experiences of non-MAPEH (Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health) teachers tasked with PE responsibilities is fundamental for promoting effective education, fostering targeted professional development, and addressing systemic issues in academic institutions (Abaño et al., 2021; Dulay, 2022; Montero et al., 2022).

This study focused on examining the experiences of non-MAPEH teachers assigned to teach volleyball in the Division of Valencia City. These teachers, lacking formal PE training, face substantial instructional challenges, including lesson preparation, technical demonstrations, performance assessment, and maintaining student engagement (Silvestre & Itaas, 2020; Solis, 2024). Broader systemic barriers, such as an overly broad MAPEH curriculum, insufficient technical supervision, limited financial resources, and inadequate access to professional development opportunities, exacerbate these difficulties (Mesias & Pelicano, 2024; Poblador & Tagare, 2022; Taboada et al., 2023). Amid growing calls for subject specialization, addressing the specific challenges of non-specialized PE teachers has become increasingly urgent.

Existing research highlights that out-of-field PE teachers experience heightened anxiety, feelings of inadequacy, diminished confidence, and psycho-emotional stress when managing PE classes (Buedron, 2018; Mesias, 2022; Solis, 2024). Although strategies such as collaboration with MAPEH majors, use of online instructional resources, and self-directed practice have been employed to mitigate these challenges (Macasias, 2022; Montero et al., 2022; Taboada et al., 2023), structured mentorship programs, resource provision, and systematic training initiatives remain insufficient (Dulay, 2022; Solis, 2024). Without coherent institutional frameworks to support non-specialist teachers, out-of-field teaching continues to jeopardize educational quality and student learning experiences (Hobbs & Porsch, 2021; Silvestre & Itaas, 2020).

While the literature outlines general challenges faced by out-of-field teachers, there remains a paucity of qualitative research exploring the localized experiences of non-MAPEH teachers assigned to teach volleyball, particularly within Philippine settings. This gap is critical because educational environments are highly contextual, and generalized findings may not adequately reflect the specific cultural, institutional, and resource-based realities confronting Filipino educators. By focusing on the Division of Valencia City, this study aimed to uncover contextualized, nuanced, and actionable insights critical for informing culturally responsive and practically feasible interventions. Situating the inquiry within a specific division enhanced the relevance and applicability of the findings, offering meaningful recommendations to stakeholders working to strengthen PE instruction in similar contexts.

Research Questions

The study aimed to address the following questions:

1. What are the challenges of the non-MAPEH teachers in teaching volleyball?
2. Based on the challenges, what coping strategies are made?

This study contributes both theoretically and practically. It enriches the growing discourse on out-of-field teaching by providing localized qualitative evidence in a Philippine context. It offers practical insights for school administrators, curriculum developers, and policymakers on designing mentorship initiatives, targeted professional development, improved resource allocation, and curriculum adaptation (Dulay, 2022; Solis, 2024; Taboada et al., 2023). At a broader societal level, this research emphasizes the importance of teacher specialization for student engagement, skill development, and sustained sports participation.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: a review of related literature to contextualize the study; a detailed description of the methodology employed; an analysis and discussion of the findings; and a conclusion offering actionable recommendations for future practice and research.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative case study design to explore the experiences of non-MAPEH teachers assigned to teach volleyball. The case study approach allowed for an in-depth examination of real-world challenges within a bounded context—Valencia City Division (Creswell & Poth, 2018). Guided by a constructivist-interpretivist paradigm, the research acknowledged that realities are socially constructed and participant experiences are best understood through subjective meanings (Lincoln & Guba, 1985).

The study was conducted in public secondary schools within the Division of Valencia City, located in Bukidnon, Philippines. These schools were significant settings because volleyball is an integrated part of the MAPEH curriculum, and the assignment of non-MAPEH teachers is common due to a shortage of specialized PE instructors (DepEd,

2020). Limited sports resources, heavy workloads, and curriculum mandates shaped participants' experiences.

Participants consisted of five non-MAPEH teachers currently assigned to teach volleyball classes. The sampling strategy used was purposive sampling, selecting individuals who met specific inclusion criteria: (1) teachers without formal MAPEH training, (2) assigned to teach volleyball, and (3) willing to share their experiences (Palinkas et al., 2015). Teachers who had formal MAPEH backgrounds or declined participation were excluded. Participants varied in age, teaching experience (ranging from 3 to 15 years), and academic specializations such as English, Science, or Social Studies.

Data were collected through semi-structured in-depth interviews using an interview guide that was developed based on the research objectives and reviewed by two qualitative research experts for content validity (Turner, 2010). Interviews were conducted via Messenger for scheduling flexibility, recorded with consent, and supported by detailed field notes. Each interview lasted between 45 to 60 minutes. Ethical protocols, including informed consent, confidentiality agreements, and the right to withdraw at any point, were strictly followed (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

Thematic analysis was used to analyze the qualitative data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Interviews were transcribed verbatim, and initial coding was performed manually. Manual coding was chosen due to the manageable sample size and to allow for a more nuanced, hands-on engagement with the data. Codes were grouped into categories based on recurring patterns, leading to the development of salient themes. Peer debriefing with an advisor and independent coding verification were conducted to ensure analytic rigor (Nowell et al., 2017).

Credibility was established through member checking, where participants reviewed and verified transcribed interviews and initial thematic interpretations (Birt et al., 2016). Dependability and confirmability were reinforced through an audit trail documenting data collection and analysis procedures. Thick description provided transferability by detailing the research context, participant characteristics, and findings (Lincoln & Guba, 1985).

The study obtained ethical clearance from the researchers' academic institution's Research Ethics Committee. Participants' rights were protected through voluntary participation, informed consent, assurance of confidentiality, anonymized data reporting, and the right to withdraw from the study at any time without consequence.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thematic analysis of in-depth interviews with five non-MAPEH teachers teaching volleyball revealed rich, nuanced, and deeply contextualized experiences. Coding involved a detailed process of transcribing interviews, identifying significant phrases through an inductive approach, grouping related codes into 11 distinct categories, and synthesizing them iteratively into four overarching themes organized according to the

study objectives. This process included multiple rounds of refinement and peer validation to ensure reliability and depth.

Table 1

Thematic Tree of Findings

Research Question	Theme	Categories	Sample Codes	Sample Quotations
1.What are the challenges of the non-MAPEH teachers in teaching volleyball?	Emotional Difficulties	Anxiety	Anxiety on out-of-field teaching	<p>“, I felt anxious about my ability to teach the sports effectively. So, ing-ana siya basin di mao ang gitudlo. Makuan pud ta.” (Participant 2, Line 54-55)</p> <p>“...at first, it's really scary that to teach a subject that is not your field of expertise. But as teachers as we are, we are actually encouraged to be flexible.” (Participant 3, Line 140-141)</p>
			Anxiety on expectations as teachers	<p>I feel guilt. Guilt in terms of you already know that I have limited knowledge of. So, medyo guilty on how to make on how to motivate the students, and how to engage them in class activities since I have limited knowledge (Participant 5, Line 69-71)</p> <p>Yeah, it's admitting to them that I have limited knowledge to this topic is a really great help for me, but I don't think teachers</p>

				are allowed to do this. I don't know because again teachers should be the most knowledgeable one in the classroom. And then it's like, if you're admitting that you don't know this, it's a very laparo to a teacher, right? It's a slap of being a teacher." (Participant 4, Line 328-332)
		Stress	Stress over teaching load	"So, makahatag siya ug stress sa non-MAPEH teachers gyud." (Participant 2, Line 196)
				"Heavy lang gyud siya. Bug-at lang gyud siya but I don't have the right to reklamo." (Participant 4, Line 103)
			Stress over teaching preparation	"Yes. Gahatag siyag stress since I said earlier na there is limited time to prepare for the subject or for the topic." (Participant 2, Line 159-160)
				Maybe the fact that there are players of the sports of the volleyball sport in my class, so it felt a little embarrassing for me because. Oh, I'm the teacher and I don't know this term. We as teachers, teachers should be the best source in the

				<p>classroom. We should be the best. Information. Yeah, we should be the best source for our learners in the classroom, right? But at that time, since I was really not prepared, that's why I gave them the copy because I wasn't prepared enough. (Participant 4, Lines 84-88)</p>
	Instructional Difficulties	Insufficient Knowledge	Lack of Knowledge	<p>I have limited knowledge and skills about the game, and since I'm not a player of a volleyball and. Uh, I'm not a sports enthusiast. So, I have difficulties in imparting my knowledge about it to my students. (Participant 2, Lines 29-31)</p> <p>"Although I have a background in my baccalaureate degree in our PE... I think my experience in college volleyball was not really enough... So when it comes to teaching, especially a sport that I have no talent in really is challenging." (Participant 4, Lines 44-58)</p>
		Inadequate Skills	Lack of expertise	<p>"I feel that my lack of physical education expertise limits my</p>

				<p>teaching effectiveness.” (Participant 1, Line 74-75).</p>
				<p>So, you know, imagine, how can an English teacher be an effective volleyball, Volleyball coach, and teacher as well...Maybe demonstrate, but not really the one that is the standard of volleyball. We can actually demonstrate, but then we never really know if it's actually the standard of serving and then the spiking as well, so I cannot really assure that I was able to give the proper knowledge to my students.” (Participant 3, Lines 35-36 and 48-50).</p>
			Low confidence on teaching delivery	<p>“And during demonstration of the basic skills, I felt awkward with my limited knowledge of the game and I since I have not formally taught it before” (Participant 2, Line 49-50)</p>
				<p>“I have low confidence. I have self-doubt that how can I teach the student how to engage them since I have self-doubt that I don't know how to</p>

				execute.” (Participant 5, Lines 60-61)
		Limited Time	Limited Time for Preparation	<p>“I have limited time to prepare for the lessons since we have other subjects to handle, and we don't have the opportunity to study more and to dig it deeper the about the game.” (Participant 2, Line 43-44)</p> <p>“So very effort gyud kaayo para sa akoo, it takes much energy from me to plan the lesson plan in MAPEH especially in sports, OK lang sa health kay makarelate relate man ta gamay. Pero sa PE gyud, lahi ra gyud.” (Participant 4, Line 183-185)</p>
			Limited Time for Teaching the Topic	<p>“Sa PE, 2 weeks. Sa 2 weeks pa gud paigoon nimo dira ang theory, ang performance” (Participant 1, Line 93)</p> <p>Oo. Kanang go outside, ano yourselves. Wa na ang 45 minutes. Wala nay time, instruction pa lang daan. And then there are a lot of students nga pag-instruct, di pa gale maminaw. So, out of in a Class, 50, for example in a grade 7,</p>

				50, so magperform sila,so, out of 15, mga 5 lang ang makaperform. So, how about the rest, pila ka time atong maextend ana?... 2 Weeks only dayon maextend pa nimo.Volleyball all about lang siya na before ka magperform, mag-introduce pa man ka.” (Participant 5, Lines 359-365)
		Classroom Management Concerns	Difficult on engaging the student	“, I have difficulty in student engagement. I mean how to maintain the students to be engaged in my discussion and the game.” (Participant 2, Line 42-44)
				“The behavior of the student is difficult to handle. Especially kung dili ka kabalo mo-manage towards your subject” (Participant 5, Line 136-137)
	Inadequate of Resources	Lack of Facilities	Insufficient Resources	“of course we are very small school, so we lack a lot of resources. Specifically, we don't have court, volleyball court. We don't have gym, we lack materials or equipments, volleyball net, what else, balls, and other.”

				(Participant 5, Line 28-30)
				<p>“We lack the equipment. Sometimes we only have one or two balls available. Sharing is a must.” (Participant 4, Line 219)</p>
			Initiatives to Provide Lacking Facilities and Equipment	<p>“Unfortunately, tagsa-tagsa nalang gyud ug pangita og way kay wala may support. Only moral support...We have to be resourceful... for our intrams.” (Participant 5, Line 391–393)</p>
				<p>“Wala pa jud, ma'am. Kami pa gyud naghimo sa poste. Kanang ligid siya, then naa man toy puthaw. Kami nanaghimo ato, initiative na namo na maghimo mi ug poste.” (Participant 1, Line 200-201)</p>
		Limited Financial Support	Limited Financial Support	<p>“Musupport siya, although musupport siya about certain sports pero walay enough na budget kay usahay baya kay daghan mga bata na gusto jud magdula pero walay budget bitaw nga ikatraining” Participant 3, Line 267-269</p>
				<p>Hinuon if eager ra pud ka as a teacher, you have to make your own way. Spend</p>

				<p>your own money. Mangita ug ways unsaon nimo. Mao naman na ron. Mangita kag ways as DepEd employee. Hinuon naa may moral support. Go! Oh, you can do it! Pero di mana mabuhat kung moral support lang, we need financial support. And then resource allocation. Kay muingon ka nga Volleyball court, dako mana siya, Volleyball Net, kaya ba nimo? (Participant E, Line 379-383)</p>
<p><i>Based on the challenges, what coping strategies are made?</i></p>	<p>Collaboration</p>	<p>Coordination with fellow MAPEH teachers</p>	<p>Collaborate with MAPEH teachers</p>	<p>“Asking guidance or resources from a MAPEH teacher” (Participant 2, Line 165)</p>
				<p>“OK, so in our school, we have one MAPEH major. I just ask that co-teacher of mine for her resources. Do you have this? Do you have that? Can you give it to me?” (Participant 4, Lines 232–234)</p>
			<p>Collaborative Expertise</p>	<p>“So maybe we will conduct a ‘lack learning action cell,’ that these three would share their techniques to their non major co-teachers who are</p>

				<p>teaching their subjects.”</p> <p>(Participant 4, Lines 480-482)</p>
				<p>“Number one is collaborate with expert. When we talk about collaboration with the expert, of course, the MAPEH is specialist or the MAPEH teachers itself. So, I have to ask everything... ask from the MAPEH teacher.” (Participant 5, Lines 145–148)</p>
		Tapping the help of Volleyball Athletes	Coordinate with Players	<p>“I will call some of my students who are volleyball players. Students nga gikan sa VNHS and was able to become part of the varsity players of VNHS.”</p> <p>(Participant 3, Lines 69-71)</p>
				<p>“I let some learners, those learners who have the skills, who are players of volleyball teach other students. So, I group them... Then I’ll assign students for every group who knows how to play... the basic skills like passing, tossing and serving.” (Participant 2, Lines 95–97)</p>
	Self-Education	Use of Sports Related Media	YouTube Videos	<p>“So sometimes I go to my very good friend, YouTube.”</p>

				<p>(Participant 4, Line 275)</p> <p>“So I have to download a lot of videos so that my students can actually relate to what I am talking about.”</p> <p>(Participant 3, Lines 141-142)</p>
				<p>“Kato sa Youtube dili mawala, Sports vlogs, and instructional books kay to gather knowledge.”</p> <p>(Participant 1, Line 151)</p>
		Self-Assessment and Practice	Practice the drills	<p>“Practicing drills before teaching the class.”</p> <p>(Participant 1, Line 104)</p>
				<p>“Ay together na siya ma’am. Bale gatuon sila, gatuon pud ko.”</p> <p>(Participant 1, Line 117)</p>
				<p>“...reading guides, importante pud na siya” (Participant 1, Line 112-113).</p>
			Self-Assessment	<p>“I don't have the right also to fail them in the performance task because I myself don't have the capacity to do those performance tasks.”</p> <p>(Participant 4, Lines 371-372)</p> <p>“I reflect on my teaching strategies,</p>

				so I have this self-assessment after I teach the volleyball. So, I reflect on what worked well or what is effective in my class. And also, what could be improved the next time I teach the volleyball game.” (Participant 2, Lines 138–141)
		Participation in Volleyball-Related Interventions	Participate in Trainings and Workshops	“, if we attend, hopefully if we attend workshop training, seminars related to volleyball. So, if we attend workshops, trainings, hopefully we gain a lot of information, develop our skills in volleyball” (Participant 5, Lines 193-195)
				“The best advice that I could give is she has to, or the teacher must enroll in a volleyball course” (Participant 6, Lines 34-35)

Objective 1: Challenges of Non-MAPEH Teachers in Teaching Volleyball

The analysis generated Three major themes: **Emotional Difficulties, Instructional Difficulties, and Inadequacy of Resources**

Theme 1: Emotional Difficulties

This theme captures the **emotional strain** non-MAPEH teachers face when teaching volleyball, focusing on **anxiety** and **stress** as key emotional challenges. These arise from teaching outside their specialization, lack of preparation, and the pressure to meet expectations.

Category 1: Anxiety Non-MAPEH teachers expressed **anxiety, guilt, and self-doubt** due to inadequate subject knowledge. They feared delivering incorrect lessons and felt they fell short of being the “most knowledgeable” in class. Literature supports that lack of training leads to fear and reluctance (Mesias, 2022; Montero et al., 2022).

Category 2: Stress Non-MAPEH teachers experienced **stress** due to time constraints, performance pressure, and unfamiliar teaching content. Many resorted to simplified delivery methods. Research confirms that lack of preparation time, especially for performance-based subjects like volleyball, contributes to burnout (Raymundo, 2021; Basalan et al., 2024).

In summary, non-MAPEH teachers experience anxiety and stress when teaching volleyball, mainly due to limited knowledge, fear of making mistakes, and pressure to meet expectations. Anxiety arises from teaching outside their field, while stress comes from heavy workloads and lack of preparation time. These emotional difficulties affect their confidence, classroom delivery, and overall teaching effectiveness. The findings highlight the importance of proper training and support for teachers assigned to unfamiliar subjects.

Theme 2: Instructional Difficulties

Non-MAPEH teachers face challenges in teaching volleyball due to insufficient knowledge, inadequate skills, time constraints, and student behavior issues. These obstacles hinder their ability to deliver effective lessons.

Category 1: Insufficient Knowledge Non-MAPEH teachers struggle with teaching volleyball because of limited knowledge. Participant 2 shared, “I have limited knowledge and skills about the game... I’m not a sports enthusiast. So, I have difficulties in imparting my knowledge about it to my students” (Participant 2, Lines 29-31). This issue is consistent with findings from Mesias (2022) and Basalan et al. (2024b), who note that non-specialist teachers struggle with content mastery, which affects their confidence and instructional ability.

Category 2: Inadequate Skills Teachers also face challenges due to a lack of technical skills in volleyball. Participant 3 mentioned, “Imagine, how can an English teacher be an effective volleyball coach... Maybe demonstrate, but not really the one that is the standard of volleyball” (Participant 3, Lines 35-36). This mirrors the findings of Silvestre and Itaas (2020), who state that teachers without expertise in PE often lack the skills necessary to properly teach and demonstrate sport techniques.

Category 3: Limited Time Time constraints significantly affect teachers' ability to effectively teach volleyball. Participant 2 explained, “I have limited time to prepare for the lessons... and we don’t have the opportunity to study more and dig deeper about the game” (Participant 2, Lines 43-44). Dulay (2022) and Taboada et al. (2023) echo this concern, noting that limited instructional time forces teachers to rush through lessons, undermining the quality of both theoretical and practical learning.

Category 4: Student Behavior Managing student behavior is particularly challenging when teachers are not confident in teaching PE. Participant 5 noted, “The behavior of the student is difficult to handle, especially if you do not know how to manage your subject” (Participant 5, Line 136-137). This is in line with Hobbs and Porsche (2021), who assert that non-MAPEH teachers, lacking specific strategies for engaging students in physical education, often struggle to maintain discipline and focus in the classroom.

Overall, non-MAPEH teachers face major challenges in teaching volleyball due to limited content knowledge, inadequate skills, and lack of training. These issues reduce their confidence in explaining and demonstrating the sport. Time constraints and large class sizes further limit effective instruction, making it hard to balance theory and practice. Additionally, poor student behavior and low engagement create difficulties in classroom management. These factors together hinder teaching quality and student learning outcomes in PE.

Theme 3: Inadequate Resources

The lack of essential resources, including facilities, equipment, and financial support, presents a significant challenge for physical education instruction, particularly for non-specialist teachers. These deficiencies hinder the quality of teaching and limit students' opportunities to engage fully in physical activities, especially in under-resourced schools.

Category One: Lack of Facilities Teachers report a lack of basic facilities and equipment, such as volleyball courts and nets. Participant 5 stated, “We don't have a court, volleyball net, balls, and other materials” (Participant 5, Lines 28-30). This aligns with Mesias and Pelicano (2024), who found that the absence of resources limits PE instruction. Teachers often rely on personal initiative to make up for these deficiencies, such as building makeshift volleyball posts (Participant 6, Lines 200-201).

Category Two: Limited Financial Support Limited budgets restrict schools from providing adequate sports facilities and training opportunities. Participant 3 shared, “There is support, but not enough budget for training” (Participant 3, Lines 267-269).

Physical education teachers, especially non-MAPEH teachers, face significant challenges due to a lack of essential facilities, teaching materials, and financial support. Schools often lack designated PE spaces like gyms and volleyball courts, limiting student engagement and skill development (Solis, 2024). Additionally, the shortage of sports equipment, such as balls and nets, restricts student participation (Subang, 2022). The lack of financial support further exacerbates these issues, as schools cannot maintain or improve PE infrastructure, forcing teachers to use personal resources (Poblador & Tagare, 2022).

Objective 2: Coping Strategies Based on Teachers' Experiences

The analysis produced two major themes: **Collaboration, and Self Education**

Theme 1: Collaboration

This theme focuses on how non-MAPEH teachers collaborate with colleagues and students to overcome their lack of training and expertise in teaching PE. Effective partnerships with MAPEH specialists and student-athletes help non-specialist teachers bridge gaps in their knowledge and improve their teaching practices.

Category 1: Coordination with Fellow MAPEH Teachers Non-MAPEH teachers often collaborate with MAPEH experts to gain teaching resources, knowledge, and support. By consulting with colleagues and accessing shared materials, they overcome instructional gaps and enhance lesson delivery (Montero et al., 2022; Katigbak & Andal, 2023). Structured peer collaboration, such as learning action cells, also fosters professional growth and improves teaching strategies (Taboada et al., 2023).

Category 2: Tapping the Help of Volleyball Athletes Non-MAPEH teachers also rely on student-athletes to assist with skill demonstrations and peer teaching. By involving students with expertise in volleyball, teachers enhance engagement and allow learners to benefit from peer-led instruction, which boosts participation and reinforces learning (Solis, 2024; Mesias, 2022).

Non-MAPEH teachers overcome their lack of expertise in teaching physical education by collaborating with MAPEH specialists and student-athletes. By working with colleagues, sharing resources, and enlisting the help of skilled students, these teachers improve their instructional strategies, enhance student engagement, and bridge the gaps in their own knowledge and skills.

Theme 2: Self-Education

Non-MAPEH teachers cope with limited formal training by engaging in self-directed learning, including watching sports-related media, reading instructional materials, and practicing volleyball drills. They also reflect on their teaching and attend seminars or workshops to build competence and confidence, showing that self-education plays a key role in improving instructional delivery.

Category 1: Use of Sports-Related Media Teachers use YouTube, sports vlogs, and instructional videos to learn techniques and plan lessons, compensating for their lack of formal PE training (Participants 1, 3, 4). This aligns with findings from Solis (2024) and Montero et al. (2022), which highlight technology as a vital tool for out-of-field teaching.

Category 2: Self-Practice and Reflection Teachers practice drills and read guides to prepare lessons and build confidence (Participant 1), and use self-assessment to adjust teaching strategies (Participant 2). This process of reflection helps them identify gaps and improve instruction, as supported by Basalan et al. (2024b) and Macasias (2022).

Category 3: Participation in Volleyball-Related Interventions Attending workshops and enrolling in volleyball courses helps teachers gain hands-on experience and formal

knowledge (Participants 5, 6). Studies by Dulay (2022) and Taboada et al. (2023) confirm that such training enhances teachers' ability to teach and demonstrate volleyball skills effectively.

Non-MAPEH teachers use self-directed strategies to compensate for their lack of formal training in volleyball. They rely on digital media like YouTube, read instructional guides, practice drills, reflect on their teaching methods, and attend workshops or training. These efforts build their confidence, enhance their teaching skills, and improve lesson delivery.

Conclusions

This study sought to capture the experiences of volleyball teaching among volleyball non-MAPEH teachers of Valencia City Division, aiming to figure out what challenges they were encountering, what coping mechanisms they were using, and what recommendations could be forwarded to help increase their ability to deliver more. This research was conducted with the aim of gaining insights into how non-MAPEH teachers who are adapting in their experience of delivering quality volleyball instruction are supported despite the fact that physical education is not their specialization, and by understanding their struggles and adaptive strategies.

The study discovered that non-MAPEH instructors endure emotional difficulties, and Instructional difficulties that restrict their effectiveness when teaching volleyball. As if the demands of discourse and pedagogy were not enough, many non-MAPEH teachers report feelings of anxiety, self-doubt, and stress from being under-trained, along with main challenges like the curriculum they need to teach, resources that may or may not be available based on their school, and limited opportunities for professional development. In spite of these challenges, teachers were resilient by seeking mentorship, availing online resources, self-education, and attending training workshops to fill in their knowledge gaps. But while individual efforts can alleviate these challenges, systemic support from schools and education policymakers is essential to ensure sustainable improvements in PE instruction.

The results of this research call for institutional reform that will help non-MAPEH teachers provide quality physical education. Schools and policymakers have to understand that out-of-field teaching harms teachers and students alike and should be addressed with targeted interventions—mentorship programs, structured training, better curriculum resources, and funding for PE instruction. Cross-training educators in subject areas they may be asked to teach in addition to their specialization should be considered for teacher preparation programs as well. This will increase teaching effectiveness in PE, as well as the PE learning experiences for all students in PE, and lead to a more competent and confident staff of teachers ensuring quality instruction for all students, regardless of their teacher's specialization.

Recommendations

The following are the recommendations to the stakeholders based on the findings of the study:

1. Non-MAPEH teachers may continue to participate in Continuous Professional Development, such as attending workshops and training sessions and using online learning resources to improve their volleyball teaching skills. They may also create fellowships with MAPEH teachers and coaches to share teaching approaches and best practices. They may introduce game-based learning and differentiated instruction to increase student engagement and accommodate lessons for varying skill levels.
2. Administrators may consider implementing mentorship and coaching programs to facilitate the care of non-MAPEH teachers by PE educators, who can provide long-term guidance and skill-building.
3. Policymakers may provide the budget for coaches and sports amenities for non-MAPEH teachers so that they can conduct volleyball lessons more efficiently.
4. Schools may allow the integration of structured lesson plans and teacher guides for PE subjects into general curricula to help clearly define and realistically fit curriculum expectations for non-specialist teachers. PE modules will then be crafted to make sure that they are accessible and organized in a way that meets the needs of non-MAPEH instructors, including detailed, systematic lesson plans, drills, and assessment strategies.
5. Curriculum Developers may create interactive digital platforms and instructional videos for non-MAPEH teachers to learn the basic concepts of teaching volleyball effectively. Teacher training programs might also provide cross-training opportunities for future educators to help prepare them for potentially being assigned to teach outside the field.
6. For the future researchers, longitudinal studies may provide insights into whether training and support programs for non-MAPEH teachers are successful over time. Non-MAPEH teachers may also be investigated on how mentorship and peer collaboration can improve their confidence and competence in teaching volleyball. Under non-MAPEH teachers, students may also be researched on their learning outcomes and how instructional strategies lead to engagement to discover its impact on student experience and skill development. This research could also be extended to other team sports and possibly other areas of PE, offering more insight into out-of-field teaching and its drivers in physical education.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this article.

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Author Contributions

All authors contributed to the conceptualization, data collection, data analysis, and writing of the manuscript. The lead researcher conducted the interviews, and thematic analysis, while co-authors assisted in peer debriefing, and manuscript revisions. All authors approved the final version of the manuscript.

Ethical Approval

The researcher adhered to the ethical standards imposed by the REC of Lourdes College Graduate School. The following were the researcher's initiatives in maintaining the study's ethics.

AI Declaration

Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools such as ChatGPT were used to assist in converting and reducing the heavily contextual thesis into a format suitable for journal article publication, with human supervision. Grammarly AI was also used for grammar and tone checking. Final interpretations, analysis, and manuscript writing were performed by the researchers.

Data Availability Statement

The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. To protect participant confidentiality, anonymized data may be shared with legitimate academic researchers subject to ethical approval.

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